

Evaluating the Environmental Sustainability of Silica Passivation for Acid Mine Drainage Treatment in Moatize's Coal Industry

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Abstract:

Acid mine drainage (AMD) is a significant environmental concern associated with coal mining. This study investigates the environmental impact of silica passivation as a method for AMD prevention. Life cycle assessment (LCA) identified a low impact on soil acidity but a substantial concern regarding climate change due to silica transportation, processing, and energy use. Scaling the findings to a large-scale mine highlights the potential for significant environmental damage from acid rain, greenhouse gas emissions, and ecotoxicity. The paper proposes strategies to improve the environmental sustainability of silica passivation, including sourcing local or recycled silica, utilizing renewable energy, developing bio-

based processing chemicals, and implementing long-term monitoring. By focusing on cleaner materials, processes, and energy sources, silica passivation can become a more sustainable solution for preventing AMD. The evaluation method can be applied to other passivation alternatives to compare and identify the most environmentally friendly approach for mine operations.

Keywords: *Life Cycle Assessment, Environmental Impact, AMD Prevention, Coal Mining.*

Introduction

The city of Moatize, Mozambique rests on a massive coal deposit, a resource filled with economic potential (Sampaio et al., 2020). Moatize's reserve claimed to be the world's largest unexploited coal field, is estimated to exceed 2.5 billion tons (Bofana, 2022; Macie & Bacci, 2017). However, this prize has a hidden threat: Acid Mine Drainage (AMD) (Egger et al.,

2021). As coal mining operations expand (Macamo, 2022), the possibility for AMD to occur is a major concern, threatening to poison the very lifeblood of the region – its water (Pondja, 2013).

AMD is a toxic cocktail born from the marriage of air, water, and exposed sulfide minerals in coal seams. This acidic, metal-laden water causes chaos in aquatic ecosystems, dissolving vital

components of life and leaving behind a sterile wasteland (Alvarenga et al., 2021). The damage extends far and wide, disrupting the fragile equilibrium of freshwater ecosystems and jeopardizing the livelihoods and well-being of communities relying on these vital resources. (Ighalo et al., 2022).

This article explores the environmental impact assessment of a promising treatment approach for Moatize's AMD: silica passivation. This method offers a potentially more sustainable solution by targeting the source of the problem – the oxidation of sulfide minerals. Silica, a naturally occurring mineral, is applied to coat the exposed sulfide minerals, forming a protective barrier that hinders their interaction with oxygen and water, ultimately reducing the generation of AMD. This scenario is grounded in a deep understanding of Moatize's unique environmental landscape – its geological makeup, existing regulations, and the limitations of current treatment technologies.

Through a rigorous evaluation of this preventative measure, this study seeks to equip stakeholders with the knowledge and tools necessary to safeguard Moatize's precious water resources and ensure the long-term sustainability of its mining industry. Ultimately, the goal is to unlock Moatize's coal's economic potential while protecting the environment and the communities that call this region home.

Literature Review

Since AMD is formed through the oxidation of sulfide minerals in the presence of oxygen, water, and microorganisms (e.g., iron-oxidizing bacteria), it follows that the exclusion of any one of these components would limit the formation of acid drainage (Elghali et al., 2023).

Recognizing that pyrite oxidation is the root cause of AMD, researchers have developed numerous methods to prevent this process from happening in the first place. These methods aim to be alternatives to traditional remediation techniques, which can unfortunately create new toxic waste in the process of cleaning up existing AMD contamination (Xu et al., 2023).

Preventing the formation of AMD is crucial for safeguarding the environment from future risks. This proactive approach offers a long-term, cost-effective solution compared to traditional remediation methods (Yang et al., 2023).

A specific example of a preventative strategy is surface passivation of sulfide minerals (Tu et al., 2022). This technique involves creating a chemically inert and protective surface coating over the sulfide surface. This coating limits the access of oxygen (O₂) and ferric ion (Fe³⁺), effectively inhibiting sulfide oxidation for an extended period (Yang et al., 2023). Silica deposition is a promising method for surface passivation. This approach entails silica deposition onto pyrite surfaces, effectively reducing the oxidation of sulfide-laden materials. Researchers have discovered that dissolving readily available, non-valuable silicate minerals found near most mine sites can neutralize acidic mine drainage. This makes silicates a promising, cost-effective, and sustainable option for managing AMD (Zhou et al., 2019). The preventative protocol involves treating tailings with a soluble silica solution, incorporating a buffering agent and a controlled concentration of an oxidizing agent, such as H₂O₂.

Silica coatings have substantiated their economic viability and enduring effectiveness, rendering them a noteworthy alternative in AMD prevention. Distinguished by their protracted resilience, silica coatings stand out as a sustainable remedy, offering a proactively robust solution for ameliorating the environmental repercussions associated with AMD when compared to certain alternatives exhibiting limited long-term efficacy (Ntshangase, 2021).

Other advantages of silica are:

- abundant in nature and can be obtained easily at relatively low costs;
- not soluble in water, and can be applied in the field without the need for continuous monitoring and maintaining a neutral pH;
- no creation of secondary pollution or eutrophication like some other methods do.

Materials and Methods

The research utilized Green Delta’s openLCA 2.0 Software (GreenDelta GmbH, Germany) and the Ecoinvent 3.10 database (Ecoinvent, Switzerland), employing ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) as the impact assessment method. This choice, owing to its widespread application in LCA studies of environmental impact assessment, facilitated the evaluation of the environmental impact of this technique used in treating AMD. The study leveraged the capabilities of openLCA for assessing ecological sustainability, to quantify resource use and environmental impacts associated with the targeted technology. While Monte Carlo simulation coupled with an adapted Z-score test was used to assess the uncertainties of the results, Origin Pro 2022 was used for statistical analyses.

LCA Framework

The LCA was well established (Ryding, 1999) and conducted following the steps presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. LCA Framework

Goal and Scope of the Study

The goal of the study was to analyze impact, in water management, of the use of silica in the passivation of coal mining tailings in Moatize, Mozambique, with the objective to prevent AMD generation.

The study used a gate-to-gate approach, focusing on the use phase of silica in the prevention of coal mining generated AMD in Moatize, and analyzed its environmental impacts on five impact categories extracted from the ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) assessment methodology, namely: climate change, terrestrial acidification, freshwater ecotoxicity, freshwater eutrophication, and water use.

While economic and social aspects were not considered, the research focused on the method’s environmental implications, using openLCA software.

Inventory

An extensive study was conducted to collect and analyze environmental data associated with coal mining activities in Mozambique, with a particular focus on the Benga project located in Moatize.

Information on inputs and outputs was derived from openLCA Software, government platforms, publications, literature, and IPCC guidelines.

Table 1 shows the life-cycle inventory inputs and outputs.

Table 1. Lifecycle Inventory Datasets - Inputs and Outputs

	Amount	Unit
INPUTS		
Tailings	1,000.0	kg
Bentonite	4.8575	kg
Electricity, high voltage, for internal use in coal mining	15.000	MWh
Hydrogen peroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	2.885.0	kg
Sodium phosphate	7.0753	kg
Sodium silicate, solid	158.18	kg
Water, river	0.5000	m ³
OUTPUTS		
Flow	Amount	Unit
Coal Mine Tailing - MZ	1,156.6	kg
sewage sludge, 97% water, WWT-SLF, hard coal ash	517.40	kg

Functional Unit (FU)

The functional unit of this study is defined as: 1,000 kg of mining waste.

This unit serves as the basis for evaluating the environmental impacts associated with the AMD prevention technology, allowing for a focused and standardized analysis.

Scenario Description

Within the framework of LCA, a scenario constitutes a picture of a potential future state relevant to a particular analysis. It is constructed upon a foundation of specific assumptions regarding future developments, and may additionally encompass the illustration of the trajectory from the present state to the envisioned future (Pesonen et al., 2000).

For the current study, Sodium Metasilicate (Na_2SiO_3) is used to prepare a soluble silica solution with a controlled pH in the range of 6-8. Phosphate buffers are used as buffering agents and a low concentration of hydrogen peroxide is added to enhance adherence and performance. Bentonite clay is used as binder. The solution is then sprayed onto 1,000 kg of tailings.

System Boundary

This study focuses on the use phase within the coal mine tailings passivation process, employing a gate-to-gate approach. Stages before and after the use phase are excluded from the analysis. While Figure 2 depicts the boundaries of the system under investigation, Figure 3 shows the material flow.

Figure 2. System Boundaries

Figure 3. Material flow diagram

Impact Assessment Methodology

The analysis employed software (OpenLCA) and a life cycle inventory database (Ecoinvent 3.10) to establish a comprehensive LCA model. This

model facilitates the evaluation of environmental impacts associated with the investigated process. Real-world data served as the foreground source, while the Ecoinvent database provides background data.

The chosen impact assessment method, ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint with the Hierarchist perspective (H), is a widely applied approach that enables the analysis of impacts at various levels. This allows for the characterization of impacts focusing on specific environmental issues. Figure 4 illustrates the selected impact categories for midpoint level.

	IMPACT CATEGORY	REFERENCE UNITY
RECIPE MIDPOINT (H)	Climate Change	kg CO₂-Eq
	Water Use	m³
	Freshwater Ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB-Eq
	Freshwater Eutrophication	kg P-Eq
	Terrestrial Acidification	kg SO₂-Eq

Figure 4. ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) Selected Impact Categories

To address the uncertainties and enhance the robustness of the findings, this study employed a Monte Carlo Simulation coupled with an adapted Z-score test.

Monte Carlo simulation is a technique that generates numerous simulations to explore a wide range of potential scenarios by accounting for inherent uncertainties (DeVore, 2017). In this study, 1,000 simulations were conducted. By employing a large number of simulations, a comprehensive collection of outcomes is produced, representing the various possibilities.

Additionally, a Z-score test, also known as the standard normal deviation test, was employed. This statistical hypothesis test assesses whether the difference between a single value and the average of a dataset is statistically significant.

Z-Score Calculation

The Z-score was calculated using the formula:

$$Z - score = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

Where:

x = The single value of interest.

μ = Mean of the dataset compared to.

σ = The standard deviation.

Adapted Z-Score Calculation

The adapted Z-score (Z_m) is calculated using the formula:

$$Z_m = |Z - score| \quad (2)$$

Hypotheses

- Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant difference between the mean of the multiple Monte Carlo simulation runs and the single value.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): There is a significant difference between the mean of the multiple Monte Carlo simulation runs and the single value.

Statistical Significance

The analysis employed a pre-defined threshold value from a standard normal distribution table to assess the statistical significance of the calculated Z_m . This comparison determines whether the observed difference is likely attributable to random chance. Common thresholds include:

- 1.96 (95% confidence level): If the absolute value of your Z-score is greater than 1.96, we can reject the null hypothesis with 95% confidence and conclude a significant difference exists.
- 2.98 (99% confidence level): A higher threshold indicates a stronger likelihood of a true difference (rejecting the null hypothesis).

Results and Discussion

Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

This section details the LCIA. The LCIA adopted the ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) method.

This methodology was implemented seamlessly within the OpenLCA 2.0 software framework developed by GreenDelta, capitalizing on the comprehensive Ecoinvent 3.10 life cycle inventory database.

The ReCiPe 2016 midpoint characterization method assessed environmental impacts using five selected indicators. The results are detailed in Table 2.

Table 2. Environmental Impact of Silica Passivation

Impact category	Reference unit	Result
Acidification: terrestrial	kg SO ₂ -Eq	631.12
Climate change	kg CO ₂ -Eq	56,541
Ecotoxicity: freshwater	kg 1,4-DCB-Eq	1,611.5
Eutrophication: freshwater	kg P-Eq	13.553
Water use	m ³	87.092

Acidification: terrestrial

The life LCA results indicate a relatively low impact on terrestrial acidification from silica passivation (631.12 kg SO₂-Eq). This positive finding aligns with the inherent properties of silica. Silica, a naturally occurring and stable mineral, resists dissolving in water and doesn't release acidic components into the environment (Monger & Kelly, 2002).

Unlike some treatment methods, silica passivation does not introduce additional acid sources. Additionally, it targets the root cause of acidification: the oxidation of pyrite in mine tailings. By creating a physical barrier, silica hinders the reactions that generate sulfuric acid, the primary driver of both acid mine drainage and terrestrial acidification (Chidiac et al., 2023). However, it's important to consider long-term effectiveness. The LCA reflects the impact during application, and monitoring is crucial to ensure the silica layer continues to prevent pyrite oxidation over time. Besides, while silica is not acidic, some processing chemicals used during silica extraction or application might have acidic properties (Pa et al., 2013). A comprehensive

understanding of the environmental impact also requires accounting for these potential contributors.

Climate change

The LCA result of a 56,541 kg CO₂-Eq climate change impact on silica passivation in tailings management demands attention.

Several factors could be contributing to this substantial carbon footprint. Obtaining the silica used in the passivation process might be a key source. Silica transportation and processing, especially if reliant on fossil fuels and long distances, can release significant greenhouse gases (Shaheen & Lipman, 2007). The passivation process itself is also quite energy-intensive. Energy production for use in the process is the top contributor to climate change.

Transporting the silica to the tailings site, and applying the passivation layer all contribute to the carbon footprint, particularly if they rely heavily on conventional energy sources like coal (Chapman, 2007). Additionally, extra chemicals are involved during silica processing and application. The production and use of these chemicals could add to the overall greenhouse gas emissions (Wernet et al., 2011).

To make silica passivation a more environmentally friendly solution pinpointing the specific activities or materials contributing the most to greenhouse gas emissions is needed. This can be achieved by breaking down the LCA results in more detail. By understanding the major contributors, we can target those areas for improvement.

Using silica located closer to the mine site would significantly reduce emissions from transportation. Another possibility is the use of silica from recycled materials, which might have a lower life cycle impact overall (CD et al., 2024). Another key area for improvement is energy efficiency. Exploring the feasibility of using renewable energy sources to power the passivation process holds immense promise. By transitioning away from fossil fuels, is possible to decrease greenhouse gas emissions associated with this process significantly (Araújo & de Medeiros, 2021).

The use of processing chemicals also requires consideration. Bio-based or less energy-intensive alternatives to current chemicals are crucial for sustainable practices (Davidson et al., 2021). LCAs comparing different options would be invaluable in identifying the most environmentally friendly solutions.

Ecotoxicity in freshwater

The LCA results for silica passivation used in tailings management reveal a specific data point: 1,611.5 kg 1,4-DCB-Eq for freshwater ecotoxicity. This finding underscores the importance of investigating potential environmental impacts on freshwater ecosystems throughout the life cycle of silica passivation as an AMD prevention strategy.

While silica is not to be found harmful, it has been tested and proved that nanosilica (Lian et al., 2019) and some silica-based xerogels (Vareda & Durães, 2017) can mobilize heavy metals within the tailings. These mobilized metals can then leach into surrounding freshwater bodies, harming aquatic life.

Chemicals used during silica processing or application (like hydrogen peroxide) can also be toxic to freshwater organisms, contributing to the observed ecotoxicity (Gaikowski et al., 1999).

Eutrophication in freshwater

The result of 13.553 kg P-Eq for freshwater eutrophication suggests a relatively low potential for this process to contribute to excessive nutrient enrichment in freshwater bodies. This is a positive finding, as eutrophication can lead to harmful algal blooms and oxygen depletion, harming aquatic ecosystems (Johnson & Hallberg, 2005).

While the LCA result suggests a low risk of eutrophication from silica passivation, it's important to acknowledge that even though the passivation process itself might not introduce significant nutrients, other factors during the life cycle could contribute. For instance, if fertilizers are used during silica production or if the processing chemicals contain nutrients, these could potentially lead to increased nutrient levels

in freshwater bodies (Constantinescu-Aruxandei & Oancea, 2023).

As the LCA likely reflects the water quality impact during the application of silica passivation, long-term monitoring is crucial to ensure the continued effectiveness of the passivation layer in preventing the release of nutrients from the tailings over time.

Water use

The water consumption associated with silica passivation appears to be relatively low, with a result of 87.092 m³. This is another positive aspect, especially considering the importance of sustainable water management in the context of coal mining activities (Zhironkin & Cehlár, 2021).

The low water consumption associated with silica passivation is a positive attribute. However, it is essential to ensure that the water source used for passivation does not compete with other vital water needs in the region. Sustainable water management practices should be prioritized when selecting a water source for the process.

The quality of the water used for passivation is also a factor. If the water itself is contaminated, it could potentially impact the surrounding freshwater environment. Pretreatment of the water used for passivation might be necessary in some cases.

Monte Carlo Simulation for Uncertainty Assessment

To assess the environmental impact variability associated with the AMD prevention method, a LCA was conducted using Monte Carlo simulation within GreenDelta's openLCA 2.0 software. 1,000 simulations were run to generate probability distributions for the environmental impact. The key findings, including average values and their associated spread (standard deviation), are summarized in Table 3.

To statistically evaluate the significance of observed differences in environmental impact between treatment methods, an adapted Z-score test was employed. This analysis compared the environmental impact of each category, obtained

from a single simulation run, to the average impact derived from multiple simulations.

Table 3. Monte Carlo Simulation Results

Impact category	Unit	Mean	Std Dev	Min.	Max.	Median	5%	95%
Climate change	kg CO ₂ -Eq	57,913	5,890.3	13,333	83,255	57,245	50,742	67,805
Ecotoxicity: freshwater	kg 1,4-DCB-Eq	3,827.1	11,943	-2,110.3	313,66	2,626.6	1,210.7	7,798.4
Eutrophication: freshwater	kg P-Eq	21.171	21.416	-23.713	513.09	16.673	6.9821	46.152
Water use	m ³	91.941	26.759	-176.94	239.46	91.544	62.471	132.92
Acidification: terrestrial	kg SO ₂ -Eq	662.06	208.33	232.31	1,663.9	625.43	378.62	1,051.6

The results, presented in Table 4, show the adapted Z-score for the selected impact category. This score indicates how many standard deviations the method's impact deviates from the overall average. By analyzing these scores, it is possible to distinguish between random variations inherent to the LCA model and statistically significant differences in the environmental effectiveness of the compared treatment methods.

Table 4. Z-Score Test Results

Impact category	Point Value	Mean	Std Dev	Z _m
Climate change	56,540	57,913	5,890.3	0.23
Ecotoxicity: freshwater	1,611.5	3,827.1	11943	0.18
Eutrophication: freshwater	13.55	21.171	21.416	0.35
Water use	87.09	91.941	26.759	0.18
Acidification: terrestrial	631.12	662.06	208.33	0.14

The Z-score analysis demonstrated a lack of statistically significant difference between the point value and the overall mean environmental impact obtained from the 1000 simulations. No absolute Z-scores reached the established thresholds for significance (1.96 or 2.58). This suggests that the observed variations in environmental impact between treatment methods may be due to random variability within the LCA model itself.

With an annual production capacity ranging from 18 to 22 million tons, the Moatize Coal

Mine Complex allocates two-thirds of its output to coking coal, with the remaining third dedicated to thermal coal (Weiler et al., 2020).

From Sample to Scale: Assessing Environmental Impact

By scaling the results obtained from a 1000kg sample (Table 2), we can assess the potential environmental impact across five key categories: terrestrial acidification, climate change, ecotoxicity, eutrophication, and water use (Table 5).

Table 5. Environmental Impact of Silica Passivation per Year

Impact category	Unit	Result (tons/year)
Acidification: terrestrial	kg SO ₂ -Eq	2.15E+08
Climate change	kg CO ₂ -Eq	1.92E+09
Ecotoxicity: freshwater	kg 1,4-DCB-Eq	5.48E+07
Eutrophication: freshwater	kg P-Eq	4.61E+05
Water use	m ³	2.96E+06

The analysis revealed a concerning picture, with significant potential harm projected in all categories for a project of this scale. This turns to a substantial contribution to environmental degradation, particularly in terms of acid rain, greenhouse gas emissions, and water resource depletion. These findings highlight the urgency of carefully considering the environmental

consequences of large-scale coal exploration projects like Moatize and exploring cleaner energy alternatives.

Conclusion

This study examined the environmental impact of using silica to prevent AMD. Overall, silica passivation shows promise, but there are some key areas for improvement, especially when considering large-scale projects.

The LCA found that silica passivation has a low impact on soil acidity. However, it also identified a significant concern regarding climate change. The high impact comes from transporting silica, processing it, and the energy used during application.

When we scale these findings up to a large mine like Moatize, which produces 18 to 22 million tons of coal per year, the potential environmental damage becomes concerning. This approach could contribute substantially to acid rain, greenhouse gas emissions, and potentially harm freshwater ecosystems.

To minimize the environmental footprint of silica passivation, we can source the silica from nearby locations significantly reducing transportation emissions or utilize recycled materials.

Powering the application process with renewable energy sources like solar or wind power is a promising approach to lessen the climate impact.

Developing processing chemicals derived from biological sources instead of those with a high environmental impact can further enhance the sustainability of this method.

Regular monitoring of the silica layer is crucial to ensure its continued effectiveness in preventing AMD over time.

It's important to remember that the LCA might not capture all the environmental impacts. Future research should compare silica passivation with other AMD prevention methods to see which has the lowest environmental footprint.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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